

Oxidative Decarboxylation : Partial Synthesis of Aegiceradienol[†] (*nor* Echinocystadienol)

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3 β -Acetoxy olean-12-en-28-oic acid (III) (acetyl oleanolic acid) on oxidative decarboxylation with lead tetraacetate-cupric acetate gave a complex diene mixture (IV) which isomerised on heating with acetic acid-hydrochloric acid to 28-*nor* olean-12,17-dien-3 β -yl acetate (V) (aegiceradienyl acetate). Hydrolysis of the acetate gave 28-*nor* olean-12,17-dien-3 β -ol (I) (aegiceradienol). 3-Oxo olean-12-en-28-oic acid (oleanonic acid) (VII) on oxidative decarboxylation gave 28-*nor* olean-12,17-dien-3-one (VI) which on reduction with sodium borohydride gave 28-*nor* olean-12,17-dien-3 β -ol (aegiceradienol).

RAO and Bose¹ isolated the first 28-*nor* olean triterpene alcohol, 28-*nor* olean-12,17-dien-3 β -ol, aegiceradienol *nor* echinocystadienol (I) from the bark of *Aegiceras majus* Gaertn. (Syn, *A. Corniculatum* Blanco) besides isorhamnetin and genin-A. Barton and Crook² prepared *nor* echinocystadienol (I) by the pyrolysis of isodehydrooleanolic acid. Noller and Carson³ prepared *nor* echinocystadienol (I) by vaccum distillation of echinocystic acid. Hansen and Lewis⁴ remarked that aegiceradienol (I) may be an artefact derived from genin-A.

Lead tetraacetate is a versatile reagent and is known to cause oxidative decarboxylation^{5,6,7}. Khastgir *et al*⁸ in connection with the work on baccatin a *nor*-triterpene peroxide from *Sapium baccatum* Roxb. subjected cratogenic acid diacetate (2 α , 3 β -diacetoxy olean 12-en-28-oic acid) to oxidative decarboxylation using lead tetraacetate and obtained 2 α , 3 β -diacetoxy 28-*nor* olean-12,17-dien. Bacha and Kochi⁹ found that cupric acetate had marked catalytic effect on the oxidative decarboxylation of primary and secondary acids by lead tetraacetate. In the present investigation oleanolic acid isolated in our laboratory from the roots of *Lantana camara* Linn¹⁰ is subjected to cupric acetate catalysed lead tetraacetate decarboxylation to aegiceradienol.

Acetyl oleanolic acid (III), on heating with lead tetraacetate-cupric acetate in dry benzene-pyridine gave an inseparable complex diene mixture (IV) which on heating with acetic acid-hydrochloric acid gave a single compound. It's physical characteristics closely resembled aegiceradienyl acetate (V) m.p. 185-187°; $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 64^\circ$ (c, 0.81 in CHCl₃); lit¹ m.p. 187-188°; $[\alpha]_D + 62$; λ max 237 and 244 nm. Hydrolysis of the acetate (V) gave the alcohol whose physical characteristics were in agreement with aegiceradienol (I) m.p. 188-190°; $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 76$ (c, 0.78 in CHCl₃); lit¹ m.p. 189-191°; $[\alpha]_D + 79^\circ$. No carboxylic carbonyl absorption in the ir spectrum. Chromium trioxide-pyridine oxidation of the alcohol (I) gave the dienone identical in all respects

with 28-*nor* olean-12,17-dien-3-one (VI) m.p. 120-122°; $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 114^\circ$ (c, 0.82 in CHCl₃); lit¹ m.p. 121-123°; $[\alpha]_D + 114^\circ$.

The above findings are substantiated by subjecting oleanonic acid (VII) to oxidative decarboxylation which also gave a complex diene mixture (VIII),

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isomerisation of which with acetic acid-hydrochloric acid gave a dienone identical with the dienone (VI) obtained above. Reduction of the dienone (VI) with sodium borohydride gave the dienol identical in all respects with the dienol (I) obtained above by the hydrolysis of dienyl acetate (V).

Direct comparison with authentic sample could not be made as it could not be secured.

Experimental

The melting points are uncorrected, ir spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 237 spectrophotometer.

Action of lead tetraacetate-cupric acetate on acetylene oleanolic acid (III): Complex diene mixture (IV): Acetyl oleanolic acid (3.5 g) was dissolved in dry benzene-pyridine mixture (4 : 1; 75 ml), lead tetraacetate (10 g) and cupric acetate (1 g) were added and gently warmed till the evolution of carbon dioxide commenced. At this point the source of heat was removed and reapplied and refluxed for 2 hr after the evolution of carbon dioxide had ceased. The reaction mixture was cooled, diluted with ether (100 ml) filtered and the residue washed with ether (3 × 100 ml). The combined ether solution (400 ml) was washed with cold sodium hydroxide (10%; 3 × 100 ml) and hydrochloric acid (2N; 3 × 50 ml). The dried ether solution gave a colourless semisolid (2 g) on removal of the solvent. It was found to be a complex diene mixture (tlc).

Isomerisation of the complex diene mixture (IV); Aegiceradienyl acetate (V): The complex diene mixture (2 g) in glacial acetic acid-conc hydrochloric acid mixture (5 : 1; 60 ml) was heated for 6 hr on water bath and diluted with water when a pale brown solid separated (1.6 g). It was chromatographed on a column of neutral alumina. Elution with benzene-pet. ether (1 : 1) gave a colourless solid (1.4 g) homogeneous on tlc. It crystallized from methanol-chloroform as colourless needles, m.p. 185-187°; $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 64^\circ$ (c, 0.81 CHCl₃); lit¹

m.p. 187-188°; $[\alpha]_D + 62^\circ$, λ_{max}^{OH} 237 and 244 nm (log ϵ 4.25 and 4.18 respectively), ν_{max} at 1725, 1760, 1240 cm⁻¹ (Found: C, 82.24; H, 10.58. C₃₁H₄₈O₂ requires C, 82.27; H, 10.65%).

Hydrolysis of aegiceradienyl acetate (V); Aegiceradienol (I): The acetate (1 g) was refluxed with methanolic potassium hydroxide (10%; 50 ml) for 1 hr. The solvent was removed and the product isolated by extraction with ether. The dried ether extract on removal of the solvent gave a pale yellow solid (0.800 g) crystallized from ethanol as colourless needles, m. p. 188-190°; $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 76$ (c 0.78 in CHCl₃); lit¹ m. p. 189-191°; $[\alpha]_D + 79$, ν_{max} (Nujol) 3630 cm⁻¹ (OH) no carboxylic (C=O) band (Found: C, 84.62, H, 11.2. C₂₉H₄₄O requires C, 84.80 and 11.3%).

Chromium trioxide-pyridine oxidation of aegiceradienol (I); 28-nor olean-12,17-dien-3-one (VI): A solution of the dienol (500 mg) in pyridine (25 ml) was treated with chromium trioxide (200 mg) and left at room temperature for 24 hr. It was then diluted with hydrochloric acid (1%; 50 ml) and extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed with dilute hydrochloric acid, water, dried and evaporated to yield a pale yellow solid. It crystallized from methanol as colourless needles m. p. 120-122°; $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 114^\circ$ (c, 0.82 in CHCl₃); lit¹ m. p. 121-123°; $[\alpha]_D + 114^\circ$, ν_{max} (Nujol) 1704 cm⁻¹ (C=O). (Found: C, 85.23; H, 10.78. C₂₉H₄₄O requires C, 85.29; H, 10.78%).

Action of lead tetraacetate-cupric acetate on oleanonic acid (VII); complex diene mixture (VIII): To a solution of oleanonic acid (2 g) in dry benzene-pyridine (4 : 1; 75 ml), lead tetraacetate (10 g) and cupric acetate (1 g) were added and gently warmed until the evolution of carbon dioxide commenced. At this point the source of heat was removed and reapplied after the evolution of carbon dioxide had ceased. The reaction mixture was then refluxed for 2 hr and worked out as above. The reaction product (1.5 g) was found to be a complex diene mixture (tlc).

Acetic acid-hydrochloric acid isomerisation of the above complex mixture (VIII): 28-nor olean-12,17-dien-3-one (VI): The diene mixture (1.5 g) was heated on a water bath for 6 hr with glacial acetic acid-concentrated hydrochloric acid (5 : 1; 60 ml) and worked out as above. The product (1.2 g) was identical with 28-nor olean-12,17-dien-3 one (VI) obtained above by chromium trioxide oxidation of aegiceradienol.

Reduction of 28-nor olean-12,17-dien-3-one (VI); Aegiceradienol (I): To a solution of the dienone (500 mg) in methanol (50 ml), sodium borohydride (500 mg) was added in small quantities for a period of 30 min and left for 2 hr. It was acidified with hydrochloric acid and extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed with water, dried and the solvent removed to yield aegiceradienol (400 mg), identical with aegiceradienol obtained above by isomerisation of the diene mixture (IV) followed by hydrolysis.

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